

Household Consumption, Inequality and Change in Nepal: Ethnicity and Class based Analysis

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Abstract

Inequality always remains at the core of discussion while talking about access to resources and opportunities and overall development in any society and country including Nepal. It is because inequality prevails in all society in different forms and degree. Whatever form and degree it would have it is ever changing. This paper explores the intra and inter group inequality in household consumption across class and social groups and describes changes taking place over a particular period of time. The necessary empirical data required for this paper are taken from secondary sources; available from NLSS III (2010/11) carried out by Central Bureau of Statistics (CBS), Nepal and Nepal Social Inclusion Survey (NSIS) carried out by the Central Department of Sociology and Anthropology (CDSA) in 2012 and the Central Department of Anthropology (CDA) in 2018. Based on the comparison of household consumption across consumption quintile as class and caste/ethnicity as social groups this paper argues that there is both inter and intragroup inequality within and between consumption quintiles; class and caste/ethnicity; social groups. More importantly, inequality found at point in time is also found in another point in time across the history. However, there is change in the form and degree of inequality in household level consumption within and between the social categories; class and social groups, over the period of time in the context of Nepal.

Key words: Household consumption, quintile and social groups, inequality and change, Nepal

1. Household Consumption and Inequality

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Modern human civilization is focused on overall human development. There are different ways of doing and developing such development. Today's development is mainly focused on improving quality of life of people. In order to improve the quality of life income is put at the center. It is often said that economy is at the driver's seat which drives most of the aspects of quality of human life. However, from sociological perspective social sphere is much important than income alone to enhance quality of human life. It is because social environment shapes the overall quality of life of people including income at individual and household level. At present, income is necessary to consume the achievements of modern development to enhance the quality of life of people. However, there are a number of things to do from the side of the state. Mishra (2007) elaborately mentions:

There are so many basics to life and society, including the state. It is neither possible nor desirable to exhaustively list them. A couple of examples will be sufficient for our purposes here. There is, as an example, and as the polar opposite of the notion of basic needs, the notion of basic capabilities. Notions of basic rights, basic obligations within and among various social-organizational levels and class and groups interests also lurk somewhere around the notions of needs and capabilities. Ideally, one would hope that needs and capabilities remain, in the medium and long term, if not in the short term, in harmony. As long as we live not merely as member of families and communities but also of a state, we would, in addition, hope that the state, as also the other societal levels and social groups, organize and "manage" resources and institutions to such an end. (Pp. 216-217)

In this context, consumption is at the core of full-filling basic needs and living standard of life of people. Therefore, it is often discussed while talking about the basic need and living standard of people in the context of each country. However, there is variation in the level of living standard and quality of life of people. It draws our attention towards looking at the inequality in various aspects of living standard and quality of life including consumption directly connected with it. Consumption based inequality is explained in

different ways. One of the ways Fisher, Johnson, Latner, Smeeding, and Thompson. (2016) discussed is:

The differences in income, consumption, and wealth across the income distribution provide insight into why it is necessary to look at income, consumption, and wealth together rather than individually. Previous research (see Fisher et al. 2015a) shows that the APC falls with income and is extremely high for the low-income households. Alternatively, wealth increases with income and yields extremely high wealth to income ratios at the highest percentiles. As a result, consumption inequality is less than income inequality, and income inequality is less than wealth inequality. This suggests that households at the bottom of the income distribution appear relatively better off using consumption as a measure of inequality at any point in time, because consumption exceeds income (and wealth) in the lower ends of the conjoint distributions. (P.46)

The household level consumption thus varies by consumption quintiles. It is because the income distribution also varies across the consumption quintiles. In this regard, Fisher, Johnson, Latner, Smeeding, and Thompson. (2016) further write:

High-income households are better off using wealth to measure relative well-being than either income or consumption because amassed wealth can be used for future consumption and for transfers across generations. Hence, our perception of relative well-being changes depending on whether we use consumption, income, or wealth. Some have estimated the flow value of wealth to add to income in order to incorporate wealth into a measure of economic well-being (Burkhauser et al. 2009; Smeeding and Thompson 2011). But regardless of the flow values, the build-up of stocks of wealth presents opportunities and advantages (or in the case of debt, disadvantages) that may in the end be more important than any flows, as Piketty (2015) argues. In our data, wealth clearly accumulates over time and financial wealth is especially prevalent in the top strata of the wealth distribution. Wealth buildup takes place when large shares of national income go to top income families (top 3 to 5 percent) who have APCs of around 0.5 to 0.6. In these

cases, high wealth and high income does not translate into consumption that is relatively as high. And so the question is what happens to unconsumed income, how does it accumulate and for what purposes, and how is economic well-being affected for such high-income and high-wealth households? None of the current analyses of inequality have fully captured the full effect of wealth on consumption and income by considering all three measures of well-being simultaneously for the same households. We know, however, that each gives a differing and important perspective on the distribution of economic well-being when considering the effects of inequality on say educational attainment of off-spring, intergenerational mobility, or even health. (P. 47)

In many cases, the average income as well as consumption is found higher in upper quintile. Whatever form of income, consumption and wealth is the distribution is usually found higher in upper quintile. Even in the case of passing on income, asset and wealth the transfer rate is also found higher in upper quintile. Therefore, rich quintile holds larger portion of income, assets and wealth while looking at the distribution across consumption quintiles. However, inequality can be discussed in different forms, dimensions and degrees.

Discussing inequality comparing different parts of world as society is usually known as special disparity. Since the political boundary of any country is usually determined by geographical areas. Therefore, spatial disparity becomes one of the important forms or aspects of inequality discussed today. In this context, Galster and Sharkey (2017) discuss about the spatial dimension as:

The first basic claim that motivates this issue is that various dimensions of inequality are organized in space. The spatial organization of inequality is, in part, simply a manifestation of inequality occurring at the level of individuals, families, and groups that is mapped on to spaces. However, spatial inequality also is due to intentional efforts to organize physical space in ways that maintain or reinforce inequality (Dreier, Mollenkopf, and Swanstrom 2001). As a result of both sets of processes, variation is tremendous in economic status, labor market opportunities,

core institutions such as schools, environmental hazards, and social networks across city blocks, neighborhoods, cities and towns, metropolitan areas, and regions. We begin with a descriptive portrait of several different dimensions of the spatial opportunity structure, focusing on the distribution across space of different segments of the population as classified by racial- ethnic background and income, economic opportunities, environmental hazards, and violence. (P. 2).

Space is thus an important dimension of inequality which gives various bases of inequality. In many societies inequality is therefore discussed in terms of city blocks, neighbourhoods, cities, towns, metropolitan areas and regions. In the context of Nepal too, inequality is often discussed on spatial basis. Such bases are rural urban, ecological regions, provinces, development regions, districts, and so on. These all bases are based on geography as the territory including administrative regions. Space is thus considered as an important dimension on the basis of which inequality is discussed. However, inequality does not remain similar forever. It changes over a period of time together with social mobility. This kind of social mobility therefore creates changes in inequality.

Arun, Annim, and Arun (2015) have discussed much about social mobility as, “Studies of social mobility have increasingly emphasised the importance of social networks as an important tenet of social capital. Most approaches within the social sciences treat social capital either as a form of productive asset or as a form of social relations (Bourdieu and Wacquant, 1992; Collier, 2002; Marques, 2011; Portes, 1998) exhibiting a degree of the liminality of social and economic processes in social mobility (P. 522)”. Social mobility is induced through various social networks of individual and households. Such networks build social capital at household level. In their studies they explore the effects of social networks on consumption behaviour in households, and they define networks that relate to participation in collectives that are formal in nature.

In the context of explaining the relationship between social networks and its relationship with social capital Arun, Annim, and Arun (2015) define social network as social capital in the beginning and explain the relationship as:

Social networks as a form of social capital are dynamic, defined as both the flow and stock of social relations based on norms and networks which enhance resource flow to households, allowing for changes in the consumption behaviour. The second section of this article identifies aspects of relationships between social capital, networks and household consumption expenditure. The third section discusses the findings from an empirical enquiry into the influence of networks on household consumption expenditure, based on the National Household Panel Survey in India. The final sections present the discussion of results and conclusions. (Pp. 522-523)

Living standard of people is usually shaped at household level. The poverty and prosperity of individuals is therefore associated with household in which individual live in. Social networks and relationship of household influences the behavior of individuals. Such behavior includes consumption behavior as well. Social networks help in developing social capital of any household and finally it also contributes in changing consumption behaviour of household member. The issue of inequality and its change remains central to almost all societies of the world. About such issue Umney (2018) writes:

It is practically impossible to discuss economy and society in Britain over the last 40 years without talking about inequality. The story is striking – as we shall see, an extended decline in inequality that followed World War II was dramatically reversed during the 1980s, and has followed a more ambiguous path since then. Because of this reversal, most people on the left in Britain see inequality as the central evil of British society, and complaining about inequality dominates left political rhetoric today. (P. 40)

Inequality changes in a particular socio-historical context. The World War II reshuffled the social and economic context of many countries of the world. During that time the prevailed inequality was changed due to many reasons. However, it is problem to discuss which inequality and in what way it is changed. In this regard, Umney (2018) further writes:

However, I argued that this was a problem. Inequality is a woolly and abstract term, and has been employed in ways that do not resonate widely. Admittedly, identifying inequality as the main social enemy has been effective in some ways, since any politician from right or left generally now needs to at least pretend to care about it. However, it has produced a fairly limited political discussion, with a fixation on technocratic measures like tinkering around with tax rates. (P. 40)

There is no doubt it is difficult to properly locate and discuss inequality and its change. It can also be discussed with identification of specific dimensions and the nature of change taking place on it. For example, the inequality of income at household level can be explained as the total amount income received by a household. The change is either increased or decreased in income. However, there are different ways of explaining inequality.

Schneider and Hastings (2017) argue that income inequality does not simply capture the distribution of household incomes at a given point in time. It can also be thought of much more broadly, as setting the context within which we define what it means to be “rich” and what it is to be “poor” (P. 482). The status of poor and rich is created due to the unequal level of income. Therefore, level of income is one of the fundamental bases of creating inequality at household level. Highlighting on this aspect of income Schneider & Hastings (2017) write:

Levels of income determine the amount and kinds of many sorts of goods that individuals can purchase. But household services are quite different. The ability to hire a maid, gardener, or cook or to purchase meals prepared by others depends not on the level of one’s income but on the gap between the income of the prospective employer and the wage of the employee. Inequality permits this kind of domestic economic arrangement and, in Jencks et al.’s (1972) telling, reveals the rich and the rest. (P. 483)

In fact, consumption of goods and services at both individual and household level is shaped by income level. Since the consumption things; goods and services, are increasing day by day more income is necessary to consume such things. In the context of many

countries, inequality is usually discussed at household level in relation to income and consumption. It has therefore drawn the attention of sociologists towards studying inequality. Schneider and Hastings (2017) report:

Sociologists have long recognized the use of domestic outsourcing by affluent households. Veblen ([1899] 1963) offers an early account of such behavior, and more contemporary accounts frame this behavior in terms of a market logic, with Bianchi et al. (2000) writing that “a higher absolute level of education may limit housework because it increases a person’s ... ability to outsource tasks.” Much of the contemporary empirical research on outsourcing in the United States makes use of the CEX, since, as Heisig (2011) notes, direct questions on the use of paid household labor are rare in representative surveys. This work documents a strong positive relationship between expenditures on household outsourcing, generally defined to include housekeeping services, laundry, and prepared meals, and household income (de Ruijter, Treas, and Cohen 2005; Treas and de Ruitjer 2008; Spitze 1999). (P. 484)

The consumption behavior of households thus changes with increasing income. The consumption behavior is also shaped by how market around is working. Expanding nature of market supports in expanding consumption behavior of individual and household. Household attempts to consume the goods and services available in the market to upgrade the quality of life of household member and household as collective form. Therefore, the nature and form of inequality in household behavior related to income, consumption, and market does not remain same forever. It is often changing.

In the context of changing nature and form of income, consumption and market the nature and form of inequality is to be explained. The changing context of social and economic environment brings various forms of social transformation. Sampson, Schachner, and Mare (2017) assume:

The location and theoretical assumptions of the urban poverty paradigm of the late twentieth century can nonetheless be challenged on at least three major fronts. One challenge comes in the form of new social transformations and crises that the

cities of classic studies have undergone. Deindustrialization, the Great Migration, violence, the growth of concentrated poverty among African Americans and population loss defined an earlier era, but many American cities in the early twenty-first century have witnessed increases in population, concentrated affluence, gentrification, and the black middle class; declines in violence; rapid immigration from around the world; the Great Recession; and rising income inequality. Referencing one of the biggest changes in American cities, the historian Michael Katz has gone as far as to argue that the explosion of immigration has “irrevocably smashed the black/white frame” (2012, 100). (P. 103)

The nature of global market is often changing with change in modern technology and neo-liberal economy. Together with change in economy, politics and society there is also change in the nature and forms of inequality of any kind. Therefore, it is important to discuss change while talking about inequality among individuals, households, communities, and so on.

2. Consumption, Inequality and Change

The history of human society shows that inequality among individual, household, groups, communities, and so on is historical and universal. It prevails in all societies across the history in different forms and degree. Now, the question is how inequality changes? There are various ideas on how inequality changes. One of the ideas is that critique change society which ultimately changes inequality as well. In this regard, Kern, Laux, and Pruisken (2017) reported important ideas as:

How does critique change society? What are the conditions for critique to emerge? These questions are the core of recent sociological discussions about social and cultural change. Since Karl Marx, there has been a long and great tradition of sociological theories placing critique at the center of their analyses by pointing at more or less contradicting principles of modern societies (Dörre, Lessenich and Rosa 2009; Habermas 1995a, 1995b; Touraine 1971). Although these "critical theories" start from different angles, they share the perception that

powerful forces such as alienation, commodification, political power, and objectivation threaten the sovereignty and self-determination subject. Hence, critique inevitably arises from the individual's pursuits for authenticity and autonomy. (P. 7)

The change in society began with the question on what is happening and why that is happening in human society. The questioning nature of humankind is also the seed of science from which modern science emerged. Whatever science developing today is the result of the looking for the reason of everything what is happening. Looking for reason ultimately gave rise to new kind of knowledge. It is also the critique on normal phenomenon in human society. It is further elaborated by Kern, Laux, and Pruiskén (2017) as:

However, despite their manifold contributions to the intellectual development of sociology as a discipline, traditional critical approaches have been often criticized themselves. A comprehensive review of this literature would exceed the scope of this article. Firstly, some researchers deprecate that the presuppositions and analytical distinctions of traditional critical theories often determine the substance of their findings (Rucht 1991; Alexander 1982). In this way, they often run the risk of oversimplifying and overgeneralizing the social, historical, and cultural circumstances that shape the causes and consequences of protest and critique. A further striking objection against traditional critical theories is that the modern, functionally differentiated society lacks of a definite moral center that provides the necessary normative basis for the "privileged" articulation of critique (Vobruba 2010, 61, 80; Vobruba 2017, 177; Luhmann 1998, 956-7). Following Max Weber (1986), modern societies consist of "value spheres" such as economy, politics, religion, science, etc. where each sphere constitutes "an autonomous universe of meaning" (Schimank 2015, 415) and follows its own kind of "value rationality" (such as profit seeking in the economic sphere, striving for power in the political sphere, and striving for truth in the sphere of science). Considering that there is no hierarchy of "values" - because all spheres make a more or less

indispensable contribution to the reproduction of social life - Weber compared the condition of modern society with a polytheistic canopy where "the gods of the various orders and values are engaged" (Weber 1958) in a constant struggle. Hence, there is no privileged philosophical, political, or religious point of view for the articulation of critique. (P. 8)

Any aspect of society or even living standard of people change with critical ideas and transforming activities. Today's scientific age, individuals and households of any society are trying to transform themselves through various ways and means. The reports published through various countries and organizations show that countries of the world are changing over the period of time. This change is taking place in all the countries. During the process of change countries are transforming from undeveloped to developing and developing to developed countries. Nepal is also trying to do so. It is therefore important to examine how the consumption behavior of various social and economic groups are changing over the period of time in the context of Nepal.

3. Objectives, Data Set and Method

Consumption is the fundamental basis of livelihood of people at household level. The amount of money household spends on various aspects of individual and household consumption determines the living standard of individual and household. This paper aims to explore the average annual household consumption by quintile groups and social groups and change over the period of half a decade in the context of Nepal.

In order to examine the average annual household level consumption and its distribution across quintile and social groups this paper borrows secondary data available in NSIS 2012 and NSIS 2018 reports published by the Central Department of Sociology and Anthropology in 2012 and the Central Department of Anthropology in 2018 respectively. Both the reports provide the average annual household consumption per capita in NRS. Based on the comparison of the available data in both the reports the change is explained in percentage. Comparing the change over the period of six years this paper analyzes how the change is taking place across quintile groups and social groups.

4. Social Class, Social Groups and Household Consumption

The average annual household consumption per capita of Nepal in 2010/11 was Rs. 18877.72. However, the distribution of pc household consumption varies across consumption quintiles and social groups. The following sections discuss the distribution of pc household consumption across quintile groups and social groups including changes over the period of time.

4.1 Consumption Quintile and Household Consumption

Consumption quintiles is created dividing the whole population into five cut points which represent 20 percent each. On the basis of this quintile groups we can understand what amount of resources is owned by a particular category of 20 percent. This quintile groups can be taken to discuss the class based features. The average annual pc household income by quintile groups is shown in table 1.

Table 1

Average Annual Per Capita Household Consumption by Quintile Groups

Quintile Groups	Mean	Std. Deviation	Coefficient of Variation
Poorest Quintile	9335.35	2166.43	4.31
Poor Quintile	13377.95	2381.25	5.62
Middle Quintile	17225.54	3385.46	5.09
Rich Quintile	22149.12	5451.71	4.06
Richest Quintile	32321.61	14381.44	2.25
Nepal	18877.72	10710.39	1.76

Source: Computed from NLSS III (2010/11) Data Set

The average annual pc household income across quintile groups ranges from Rs. 9335.35 for poorest quintile to Rs. 32321.61 for richest quintile. The average annual pc household income of richest quintile is three times higher than that of poorest quintile. The difference is increasing by about of Rs. 4000 from poorest quintile to rich quintile. The difference is largest between rich and richest quintile. The difference is of about Rs.

10000. However, the average annual pc household consumption of middle and rich quintile is closer to national average annual pc household income of Nepal.

There is also intragroup inequality among the household of all quintile groups. However, the variation ranges from 2.25 (CV) in richest quintile to 5.62 (CV) in poor quintile. The intragroup inequality is highest among the household of poor quintiles (CV=5.62) followed by middle quintile (CV=5.09). The overall inequality of Nepal is lowest compared to the inequality among the households of all quintile groups.

4.2 Consumption Quintile, Household Consumption and Change

The income and consumption behavior of households is changing all over the world including Nepal. The rate of change is faster among the households of developing countries compared to developed countries. However, we can observe ups and downs in the changing nature of consumption nature of households. The average annual pc household consumption in 2012 and 2012 and the change over the period of about half decade in shown in table 2.

Table 2

Average Annual Household Consumption Per Capita (NRS in '000) and Its Percentage Change by Quintile Groups

Quintile Groups	Average consumption 2012	HH consumption 2018	% change
Poorest Quintile	20.4	42.8	110.4
Poor Quintile	26.1	45.7	74.8
Middle Quintile	30.2	51.2	69.7
Rich Quintile	36.7	55.5	51.4
Richest Quintile	57.6	81.6	41.8
Nepal	37.3	63.8	71.2

Source: NSIS, 2018 (CDA)

The average annual pc household consumption across quintile groups ranges from 20.4 thousand for poorest quintile to 57.6 thousand for richest quintile. There is the difference

of about six thousand rupees for each group from poorest quintile to rich quintile. The difference is higher between the rich and the richest quintile. The difference is about of twenty thousand rupees.

The average annual pc household consumption is found significantly increased from 2012 to 2018. The change seems more interesting in the case of poorest quintile. The average annual pc household income of this quintile groups is found increased from 20.4 thousand rupees to 42.8 thousand rupees which is almost double. The percentage of change is 110.4 percent. It is interesting to note that the consumption of level of lowest quintile is also increasing faster compared to other quintiles over the period of time.

The average annual pc household consumption ranges from 42.8 thousand rupees to 81.6 thousand rupees in 2018. It seems that even in the case of richest quintile there is remarkable change. The average annual pc household income among the households of richest quintile is changed with 41.8 percent. It indicates that the rate of change or increase in average annual pc household consumption in Nepal is faster. Even the households in poor and poorest quintile are making significant increase in average annual pc household consumption. It is interesting to note that the rate of increase in average annual pc household consumption is faster among poorest and poor quintile compared to rich and richest quintile.

4.3 Social Groups, Household Consumption, Inequality and Change

Social diversity and inequality is another important aspect while discussing inequality and change. Nepal's diversity is rich in terms of caste and ethnicity. The categories made on the basis of caste and ethnicity is defined as social groups. All the caste and ethnicity are grouped under 11 major social groups to discuss consumption based inequality. These major social groups listed for the purpose of analyzing inclusion and exclusion status of individuals and households are discussed here for the purpose of discussing inequality. It is important to understand the status of average annual pc household consumption across household and its change over the period of half decade. The distribution of average annual pc household consumption across social groups is shown in table 3.

Table 3

Average Annual Household Consumption Per Capita (NRs) by Social Groups

Quintile Groups	Average consumption 2012	HH	Average consumption 2018	HH	% change
Hill Brahman	67684		104768		119.7
Hill Chhettri	38809		68823		77.3
Madhesi B/C	43188		67970		57.4
Madhesi OC	32290		48162		49.2
Hill Dalit	26073		45303		73.8
Madhesi Dalit	23373		35823		53.3
Newar	54432		95001		74.5
Mt./Hill Janajati	35198		59605		69.3
Tarai Janajati	35283		48656		37.9
Muslim	34922		48160		37.9
Marwadi	99261		98585		-0.7
All Nepal	37369		63861		70.9

Source: NSIS, 2018 (CDA)

The average annual pc household consumption varies across social groups and also varies over the period of time. The average annual pc household consumption in the year 2012 ranges from Rs. 23373 for Madheshi Dalit to Rs. 99261 for Marwadi. This shows that the range is much higher; about five times of the social groups (Madheshi dalit) with lowest pc household consumption. Similarly, next social groups with second highest average annual pc household consumption is hill Brahman with Rs. 67684. The average annual pc household consumption is found increased for the year 2018. The lowest average annual pc household consumption is Rs. 35823 for Madheshi Dalit.

The average annual pc household consumption is found increased in the year 2018. The lowest level of average annual pc household consumption is of the same social groups, i.e. Madheshi Dalit (Rs. 35823).in the year 2018 as well. However, the growth is double of the average annual pc household consumption of the year 2012. The increase in

average annual per capita household consumption is common to all social groups although rate of change is different for different social group. It is interesting to note that the rate of change in the average annual per capita household consumption among Hill Brahman is 119.7 percent. In contrast, the average annual per capita household consumption in Marwardi social groups is found decreased for the year 2018 by 0.7 percent. The rate of change is higher among Newar (74.5%), Hill Dalit (73.8%) and Mt./Hill Janajati (69.3%). This shows that there is increase in average annual per capita household consumption among all social groups. However, the rate of change differs from one social group to another.

5. Conclusions

Consumption behavior of household and household consumption level can be regarded as one of the key indicators of standard of living of people. It determines the quality of life of people as well. Since the consumption behavior of household is connected with the income level of household individuals and households make effort to increase income level of household on regular basis. This kind of individual and household effort is contributing in changing household consumption in all the countries of the world including Nepal.

The average annual per capita household is unequally distribution across the households of quintile and social groups in Nepal. The intra-group inequality that exist within each quintile which makes an important sense in understanding variation in the living standard of people. The level of inequality is highest among poor and middle quintile followed by poorest quintile compared to richest quintile. The intragroup inequality is lowest among the households of richest quintile. More importantly, the overall inequality in average annual per capita household consumption of Nepal is lower compared to intra-group inequality across all quintiles. There is change in average annual per capita household consumption among all quintile groups. The change seems higher in poorest quintile which is an important indicator of changing economic status of poor households.

There is also variation in the distribution of average annual per capita household consumption across social groups of Nepal. Tarai Dalit is found with the lowest average annual per capita household consumption in different points in time over the period of short history. The

social groups with highest average annual pc household consumption is found among Marwadi in 2012 and among Hill Brahman in 2018. However, there is also change in the average annual pc household consumption among all social groups including the social groups with lowest and highest level of consumption. It is to be noted that the change in average annual pc household consumption in Hill Brahman social group is more than double of the previous average annual pc household consumption of 2012. There is unequal level of average annual pc household consumption among social groups. However, there is change in average annual pc household consumption among all social groups. Thus, there is unequal distribution of average pc household consumption across quintile and social groups. Inequality among quintile and social groups seems prevailed in every point in time and there is also inter and intragroup inequality which is changing over the period of time.

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Annex: 1

Social Groups of Nepal

Hill Brahman (12.2%): Hill Brahman [1]

Hill Chhettri (19.1%): Chhettri, Thakuri and Sanyasi/Dashnami [3]

Madhesi Brahman/Chhettri (0.8%): Brahman, Kayastha, Rajput [3]

Madhesi Other Caste (14.5%): Badhae/Kamar, Baniya/Kathabaniya, Baraee, Bin/Binda, Bhediyar/Gaderi, Hajam/Thakur, Haluwal, Kahar, Kalwar, Kanu, Kewat, Koiri/Kushwaha, Kumhar, Kurmi, Lodha, Lohar, Mali, Mallah, Nuniya, Rajbhar, Sonar, Sudhi, Teli, Yadav [24]

Hill Dalit (8.1%): Badi, Damai/Dholi, Gaine, Kami, Sarki [5]

Madhesi Dalit (4.7%): Bantar/Sardar, Chamar/Harijan/Ram, Dhobi, Dom, Dusadh/Pasawan/Pasi, Halkhor, Khatwe, Musahar, Tatma/Tatwa [9]

Newar (5.0%): Newar [1]

Mountain/Hill Janajati (22.2%): Bhote/Walung, Bote, Baramu, Byasi, Chepang, Chhantyal, Danuwar, Darai, Dura, Bhujel, Gurung, Hayu, Yholmo, Jirel, Kumal, Lepcha, Limbu, Magar, Majhi, Pahari, Rai, Raji, Sherpa, Sunuwar, Tamang, Thakali, Thami, Yakha [28]

Tarai Janajati (8.6%): Dhanuk, Dhimal, Gangai, Jhagad, Kisan, Koche, Meche, Munda/Mudiyari, Rajbansi, Santhal, Tajpuriya, Tharu [12]

Muslim (4.4%): Muslim [1]

Other (0.4%): Marwadi [1; 0/2%]